

A STUDY OF THE ELECTROMAGNETIC PROPERTIES OF IRON-MULTIWALLED CARBON NANOTUBES COMPOSITES

G.Liu¹, J W Bao¹, J M Sun², Y Zhao^{2*},

¹ National Key Laboratory of Advanced Composites, AVIC Composites Center, Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials, Beijing, China

² School of Materials Science&Engineering, Beihang University, Beijing, China

* Corresponding author (Jennyzhaoyan@buaa.edu.cn)

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1. Introduction

Because of their excellent mechanical properties and electrical properties, carbon nanotubes have been the research focus in materials of physics and chemistry [1-2]. Carbon nanotubes have been widely applied in electronic devices [3], absorbing materials and reinforcements [4]. However, because of the weak magnetic properties of carbon nanotubes, they can hardly be used in electromagnetic shielding. At present, many researchers have enhanced their magnetic properties by covering iron, cobalt or nickel via chemical modification, Such as electroless plating, electroplating [5] and chemical vapor deposition [6]. Electroless Plating initiates metal deposition on the surface of the substrate from the catalytic active center. So it has the advantage of small plating grains and low porosity which other modifications do not possess. Xue [7] covered iron-cobalt alloy with utilizing eletroless plating. Because iron does not have catalytic activity, there are little reports about it used in electroless plating. However, iron has high saturation magnetization value. There are many new properties when nano-iron is covered on the surface of carbon nanotubes [8]. Then the modified carbon nanotubes can be used in structure-function integrated composite material. In this study, electroless plating was used to coat Fe on the multi-walled carbon nanotubes' surface and the electromagnetic parameters of MWCNTs composites, Fe-MWCNTs composites were measured to calculate absorbing properties. It is found that the microwave

absorption properties of MWCNTs composites are improved.

2. experiment section

2.1. Electroless plating Fe onto MWCNTs' surface

MWCNTs were purchased from Shenzhen Nanoport Company, and the purity was claimed to be 95% by the manufacturer. The MWCNTs were purified by ultra-sonication in a concentrated sulfuric acid/nitric acid (3:1, v/v) for 4 hours. The purified MWCNTs were filled in the aqueous solution of SnCl₂ and concentrated muriatic acid to reacting for 60min followed by filtrating and drying. Then the MWCNTs particles were filled into the aqueous solution of PdCl₂ and concentrated muriatic acid to reacting for another 60min. The as-prepared MWCNTs were finally filled in the aqueous solution of Na₃C₆H₅O₇, FeSO₄·7H₂O and NaH₂PO₂. The pH of the solution was adjusted by ammonia. The reaction continued until no bubbles arising. The solution was filtrated under vacuum and the as-prepared Fe-MWCNTs were dried in a vacuum drier.

2.2. Material characterization

The morphology of MWCNTs was observed by field-emission scanning electron microscope (Apollo-300 OXFORD Corporation) and Transmission Electron Microscope (JEM-2100F) as well as the elemental components was presented by the energy-dispersive X-ray detector (EDX, HORIBAEX-250). X-ray diffraction pattern was tested by D/max diffraction instrument. Static magnetic properties were obtained by Vibrating

Sample Magnetometer (LDJ9600). Electromagnetic parameters were tested by Vector network analyzer (HP-8722ES)

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Mechanism of covering Fe on surface of CNTs by electroless plating

A large number of hydroxyl groups and carboxyl groups were produced after pretreating CNTs [9]. The two kind groups are strongly nucleophilic and attached Sn^{2+} to the surface of CNTs. After that, the Pd^{2+} is reduced by Sn^{2+} to become catalytically active center which caused nano-iron produced on the surface of CNTs. The chemical equations are as follows:

3.2 Analysis of Fe-CNTs' morphology

The surface of original CNTs (Fig. 1a) is smooth, while that of Fe-CNTs (Fig. 1b) is coarse. At the same time, little free iron can be observed by FESEM. The results show that iron is covered on the surface of CNTs. To obtain the result of the Fe-MWCNTs with the method of the electroless plating, the morphology of the Fe-MWCNTs is observed with FESEM. Black dots (Fig. 2b) are seen on the surface of the nanotubes, which indicated that the metal has been coated on the surface of the nanotubes, since in the FESEM image of original materials (Fig. 2a), no such black dots exist. Furthermore, the element content of iron is ~15wt% known from the EDS. From Electron diffraction images of Fe-MWCNTs (Fig. 2c) manifest existence of polycrystalline. And the HRTEM figure (Fig. 2d) shows the interline spacing is ~0.203nm, which proves the existence of bcc-type Fe (JCPDS card NO.06-0696).

3.3 Analysis of the metal structure covered on the CNTs' surface

XRD patterns of the Fe-MWCNTs are also tested to further ensure the existing of Fe, as shown in Fig. 3. For Fe-MWCNTs, the diffraction peaks at $2\theta=44.5^\circ$, 65.2° and 82.3° can be well indexed to the cubic bcc-type Fe crystals.

3.4 Research on static magnetic properties of Fe-CNTs

To estimate the magnetic properties of as-synthesized samples, the magnetic hysteresis loops at 300K are characterized, as shown in Fig. 4. The curve of O-MWCNTs (Fig. 4a) is such a horizontal line that no magnetic features are observed, which corroborates the fact that O-MWCNTs is a non-magnetic material. In contrast, the result of Fe-MWCNTs is an S-shaped loop (Fig. 4b), from which we can learn that the saturation magnetization value reaches 15.18emu/g and the coercivity is about 13.95Oe. Such characteristics suggest that Fe-MWCNTs nano-composites are a kind of ferromagnetic materials with small hysteresis area and they can be easily magnetized [10].

3.5 Research on electromagnetic properties of Fe-CNTs

In the test, the paraffin wax was used as a binder. The CNTs powder was made cylinder whose inner diameter of 3mm, outer diameter of 7mm, thickness of 2mm. The content of CNTs was 20wt%. From Figures of electromagnetic parameters (Fig 5), the original CNTs have higher dielectric constant than Fe-CNTs'. Fe-CNTs' real part of permittivity is about 7 at range of 2-18GHz. While imaginary part of permittivity is just about 0.7. The real part of permeability ranges from 0.96 to 1.02. Imaginary part of permeability gradually decreases, which is good for expanding absorption band [11]. Compared with the original CNTs, dielectric constant of Fe-CNTs is lower. The reason is that CNTs' graphite structure was damaged in the process of electroless plating. From the above analysis, the results show that

Fe-CNTs' magnetization performance improves, but its magnetic loss slightly declines.

For further investigation of the microwave absorption, the reflection loss of MWCNTs and Fe-MWCNTs are calculated. The reflection loss curves of MWCNTs, Fe-MWCNTs are shown in Fig. 6. The reflection loss of a microwave absorbing layer is given by

$$R=20\lg|\Gamma| \quad (1)$$

$$\Gamma=\frac{Z_{in}-Z_0}{Z_{in}+Z_0} \quad (2)$$

$$Z_{in}=Z_0\sqrt{\frac{\mu_r}{\epsilon_r}}\tanh\left[\frac{j2\pi d}{\lambda}\sqrt{\epsilon_r\mu_r}\right] \quad (3)$$

Where Z_{in} is the normalized input impedance, c is the velocity of electromagnetic waves in free space, and d is the thickness of the absorbing layer.

The reflection loss of original CNTs and Fe-CNTs are negative number, which means both of them absorb the microwaves. The R of original CNTs reaches the lowest point at 16.0GHz. While the lowest point of Fe-CNTs' R is -7.0dB at 17.5GHz. At the same time, the frequency width of the $R < -5$ dB is 4GHz. Combined with the electromagnetic parameters, the reason for the result is that Fe-CNTs' impedance matching and loss matching is better than original CNTs' [11].

4. Conclusion

In this study, the cubic bcc-type iron is covered on the surface of CNTs with electroless plating. The static magnetic properties have largely improved, and the saturation magnetization reaches 15.18emu/g. At the same time, the absorbing properties have also increased, which means the Fe-CNTs can be used as absorbers in the structure-function integrated composite material.

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Fig. 1. FESEM images of MWCNTs: a O-MWCNTs; b Fe-MWCNTs

Fig. 2. TEM images of MWCNTs: a and b. O-MWCNTs; c and d. Fe-MWCNTs

Fig. 3. XRD patterns of MWCNTs: a O-MWCNTs; b Fe-MWCNTs

Fig. 4. The hysteresis loops of MWCNTs: a. O-MWCNTs; b. Fe-MWCNTs

Fig. 5. The complex permeability of MWCNTs: a O-MWCNTs; b Fe-MWCNTs

Fig. 6. The reflection loss curves of MWCNTs: a. O-MWCNTs; b. Fe-MWCNTs;

Table. 1 The saturation magnetization and coercivity of MWCNTs

	Ms(emu/g)	Hc(Oe)
O-MWCNTs	0.16	-
Fe-MWCNTs	15.18	13.59